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On streamlining data reporting and data sharing practices for promoting research reproducibility in screen-based neuromarketing studies

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Introduction

- Neuromarketing and Eye-tracking academic and business growth

Number of Neuromarketing and Eye-Tracking Articles Published (2004-2023)

Neuromarketing and Eye-Tracking Market Size (2015-2030)

Motivation

- **Are there devices/sensors** that can directly measure high-level cognitive human emotional responses?
- **The capabilities of Eye-Tracking (ET) and Electroencephalogram (EEG) sensors are sometimes overestimated**
- **Lack of widely accepted conventions across studies in variables and measures**
- **Lack of reproducibility due to limited raw sensor data sharing**

Contribution

1. **Re-iterate technological limitations of ET and EEG sensors.**
2. **Pinpoint underdiscussed reasons** for cross-study inconsistencies, that hinder research reproducibility.
3. **Highlight the importance of standardization** in data reporting and **provide further incentives** for raw data sharing.
4. **Propose a set of good data reporting practices** that may be adopted in ET and EEG marketing studies by researchers.
 - Or be used as a “checklist” by reviewers and journal editors.

Limitations of ET and EEG sensors

1. Technological limitations of ET sensors

- **ET sensors work optimally under the manufacturer-defined conditions:**
 - And it varies across different participants (age, ophthalmic conditions, wearing glasses etc.), light conditions, across different participant distances from the screen.
 - There is no guarantee that they work under different conditions.
- **ET sensors cannot calculate attention. They can only estimate the gaze direction over time, i.e.,**
 - 4D signal over time estimating the relative/normalized (0-1) X, Y gaze direction, and can also be 6D if the sensor can also output the pupil diameter
- **All other variables such as fixations, saccades, gaze paths, attention maps etc. are extracted by algorithmic processing of the raw data.**

1. EEG signals

- **EEGs measure the brain's electrical activity:**
 - through non-invasive scalp electrodes.
- **EEG analysis includes:**
 - spectral analysis to examine signal frequencies
 - hemispheric asymmetry to compare brain hemispheres
 - and calculation of statistical indices correlated to some given marketing stimuli
- **The most widely used brain activity metrics are:**
 - Approach-Withdrawal index
 - the Global Field Power
 - the Memorization Index
 - the Pleasantness Index

1. EEG limitations

- **EEG signals are susceptible to noise**
 - electrical interference from the environment, artifacts from muscle movements (e.g., eye blinks, jaw clenches), and even heartbeats.
- **EEG signals are non-stationary, i.e., their statistical properties are changing over time.**
 - This variability can occur even within a session due to fatigue, boredom, or varying levels of engagement.
- **There can be significant variability in EEG responses both within a single session, across different sessions, and between different subjects.**
 - stemming from individual differences in brain anatomy, psychological states, and other factors.
- **The quality and relevance of the EEG data depend significantly on the precise placement of electrodes on the scalp.**
 - Incorrect placement can lead to poor signal quality or the misinterpretation of where brain activity is originating.
- **Standardized electrode placement protocols like the 10-20 system are used to ensure consistency and comparability of data across studies.**

Examples of studies

2. Eye-tracking studies in marketing

Study 1

- AOI definition:
The AOI defined on the bottom right, is a lot larger than the actual button

Study 2

- AOI definition:
Here AOI sizes were defined at the 115% of the actual stimuli size (reported)

Frade et. al (2022). Skippable or non-skippable? Pre-roll or mid-roll? Visual attention and effectiveness of in-stream ads. *IJA*, 42(8), 1242–1266.

J. Pfiffelmann et al (2020). Personalized advertisements with integration of names and photographs: An eye-tracking experiment. *JBR*, 111,196–207

2. Multisensor Neuromarketing study

Study 3

- EEG, EDA, BVP
- Reported variables:
 - “Percentages (0-100%)” of:
 - Fear, attention, valence, memorization

- Are some values exceeding the variable range (0-100)?
- Are percentages >100% or negative?

Mas et al. (2024). Emotions in fear communication: A cross-cultural neuromarketing approach. *Psychology & Marketing*, 41, 697–718.

Experimental protocol Checklist

3. ET experimental protocol reporting checklist

- **Equipment and software**
 - Device name, configuration, sampling rate
 - Software for acquiring and processing the data
- **Scene geometry and experimental conditions:**
 - Screen size and resolution
 - Stimuli size in pixels
 - Distance of participants from the screen/sensor
 - Light conditions
- **Core variables and data quality:**
 - What is the definition of a fixation in this study? 80ms, 150ms, 250ms?
 - Was calibration performed per subject? What was the average error?
 - Further data quality checks (as in saturation, variance across participants, etc.)
- **AOI definition:**
 - If square, it should be reported in coordinates respective to the visual material:
 - AOI center (x,y), height, width
 - Intersection over Union (IoU) ,metric (0-100) of the defined AOI area with the stimuli

3. EEG experimental protocol reporting checklist

■ Equipment

- Device type and model number
- Number of EEG channels
- Configuration (montage: bipolar, or referential)
- Type of EEG electrodes (dry or wet)
- EEG reference selection, sampling frequency, filtering
- Recording of supplementary data such as electrooculograms (EOG) signals and eye tracking data
- It is common to **pre-process** the signals to remove artifacts and noise
 - the **adopted specialized software** must be reported together with its configuration.
 - The **algorithms** used for data pre-processing

Data sharing incentives and best practices

4. Good data sharing practices

- **The most trivial way is to share the raw sensor data, publicly and openly**
 - When enough raw data are shared, open and free tools to analyse them will emerge and become more popular (EEG Lab, Pygaze, etc.)
- **How to share?**
 - OSF, Zenodo, University repositories or Open-research Europe all feature DOI assignment, and fulfill all data management prerequisites
 - Github should also be considered for sharing codes
- **When raw data sharing is not possible:**
 - We incentivize to share as many extracted variables as possible, even if they are not related to the study, in open data formats (most sensors allow it)
 - They can be in some appendix or a separate file, attached with the study

4. Incentives for data sharing

- **Data and code sharing can significantly increase article impact (and citation count)**
- **Stimulates further studies within the domain**
 - A meta-analysis study might use them and reference this paper
- **Enables studies outside the domain**
 - Attention heatmaps can be used in computer vision for saliency detection problems (1000+ citations for an article that did it in 2020).
- **Promotes the development of new and existing open-source tools**
- **Long-term benefits**
 - Reduces complexity and costs for conducting experiments
- **There are no real ethics constraints!!!**
 - Sensor data are not personal data, if they are (pseudo-)anonymized
 - Even in the case of facial images/videos, significant effort is needed for re-identification

Conclusion

- We **discussed** the **technical details** that ET and EEG works in marketing should take into consideration.
- We proposed a set of minimum reporting protocol that should be followed in order to **promote and facilitate cross study coherence and research reproducibility**.
- Adopting our proposal as a baseline checklist can **facilitate the work of the reviewers by requesting specific details in the experimental settings**.
- **These practices can enhance the quality of the articles and their impact to the domain and outside**, without significant additional workload to the researchers.

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Thank you!

Q & A

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